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**Guide and Recommendations for
End-Users and Policymakers on the
Duly Promotion, Creation,
Implementation and Management of
Social-and-Education-Centred Energy
Communities**

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Executive Summary

The AURORA project has shown that it is possible to engage citizens more actively in the energy transition, not just through information campaigns, but by fostering real involvement based on direct experiences and behavioural change. Rather than targeting only those already motivated by climate change concerns, AURORA set out to build a broader and more diverse community—one that brings together a variety of opinions, attitudes, and levels of engagement. This inclusivity has been one of the project’s key strengths: the goal was not to preach to the converted, but to open spaces where different types of citizens could come together, participate, reflect, and take action.

To that end, the project developed “hubs”—community-based spaces for action—within pre-existing social settings such as universities and neighbourhoods, which remained active over a two-year period. The intervention carried out in these hubs followed a four-phase structure. First, each hub was designed based on the general guidelines presented in the “Mobilization” section of this guide, but with a strong emphasis on local adaptation. This localization process was carried out in a participatory way, involving hub members from the outset. Their input helped ensure the relevance of activities while also identifying in advance the specific drivers and barriers likely to arise in each context.

From the beginning, the project emphasized the importance of real-life experiences in fostering meaningful learning. Access to personalized energy data was therefore a central pillar of AURORA’s approach. While various tools are available for this purpose, the project chose to develop its own platform based on the concept of labelling. This tool allows citizens to assess their real energy behaviour using their own data and provides a clear, user-friendly overview of consumption patterns. The platform is now available for use across all 27 EU Member States.

In a later phase, this tool was complemented with a smart recommendation system that analyses individual energy-use patterns and provides personalized, actionable suggestions for improvement. With this information, citizens were invited to engage in real-world experiences that helped them understand how to improve their behaviour and take a more active role in the energy transition.

The range of activities implemented across the hubs was broad and diverse, as reflected in this guide. One of AURORA's main innovations was to go beyond traditional energy-efficiency workshops and incorporate the concept of the energy community. By doing so, the project emphasized not only individual action but also the legal and social capacity of communities to drive change through the promotion of renewable energy. This helped strengthen local commitment and foster a stronger sense of collective responsibility.

Importantly, AURORA's ambition extended beyond individual transformation. The project also sought to lay the foundations for continuity and scaling. To this end, a network of ambassadors was established, allowing the most engaged participants to support the creation of new hubs in other communities and help spread the model further.

Throughout the process, each hub maintained a strong commitment to communication, using locally adapted channels and messages to maximize engagement and visibility. This combination of lived experience, personalization, community-building, and strategic communication has been one of AURORA's most valuable contributions.

Thus, this guide is intended as a reference for the implementation and recommendation of such hubs in different locations. To facilitate replication, and although it includes real examples of how AURORA has been implemented, **the guide is not written in a prescriptive way but rather in general terms.** It offers a flexible and adaptable framework that allows other communities, institutions, or groups to apply the project's principles according to their own local contexts, available resources, and socio-cultural characteristics. The **aim is not to provide a rigid formula, but rather a starting point**—one that empowers each new hub to find its own path toward citizen engagement in the energy transition.

Dr. Ana B. Cristóbal

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Context

Energy plays a pivotal role in achieving climate goals, as outlined in the European Green Deal ^[1] from a European perspective, and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) from a global standpoint. This is due to the significant environmental impact of both individual and collective energy choices.

The overall global outlook, as published in November 2024 ^[2], still presents major challenges for the energy sector. This sector—which includes electricity, heating, and transport—is the largest contributor to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, responsible for approximately 73% of the total. The European outlook, published by the European Parliament in 2024, reflects a similar pattern ^[3].

The European Green Deal sets out an ambitious framework to drastically cut greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, foster innovation, and protect the environment. At its core is climate action, embodied in the 2030 Climate Target Plan^[4]. While the accompanying impact assessment ^[5] outlines key measures for decarbonization, it relies heavily on policy-driven scenarios—focusing on fuel prices, technology, investments, and regulations—while paying little attention to the potential role of consumer behaviour in reducing emissions. Within this framework, Table 1 highlights key actions and indicators for transforming the energy system, emphasizing the need to scale up renewable energy and reduce energy demand, both essential for achieving the targeted GHG reductions across sectors.

Actions to achieve 50% to 55% GHGs reductions by 2030		Key indicators
Energy demand	General	↓19%-21% compared to 2015
	Industrial	↓ 25-28% compared to 2015
	Transport	↓ 14-16% compared to 2015
	Residential	↓ 22%-25% compared to 2015
Increase renewables		From 15% of Gross Inland Consumption -GIC- in 2015 (around 18% today) to 31%-34% in 2030

Table 1. Key actions and indicators to achieve a sectoral transformation in the energy system. Extracted from [6] to achieve the expected Greenhouse Gases reductions.

However, the scenarios included in the studies supporting the Climate Pact, although highlighting the objectives of reducing energy consumption and increasing the

share of renewables, fail to consider the influence of social acceptance and behavioural change in achieving these goals. Notably, the potential reduction in energy demand through behavioural adjustments by citizens is entirely overlooked in these models. This omission represents a missed opportunity to empower individuals and communities in the climate transition and, more critically, contributes to growing societal resistance to renewable energy infrastructure. A decade ago, social acceptance of renewables was far more favourable. The current top-down approach—driven by technology and targets but neglecting people's voices—has begun to create tensions where there were none. True transformation must include the people, not just policy and technology.

Achieving such behavioural modifications requires strategic interventions, some designed and studied in recent years. These include awareness campaigns, incentive structures, participatory planning processes, and education, all of which can drive lasting changes in energy consumption habits and foster societal ownership of the green transition^[7].

Types of actions implemented to drive changes

To encourage changes in energy consumption—reducing usage and shifting to clean sources—effective policies are needed beyond social norms although understanding psychological and social factors is crucial for policy success^[8, 9]. Some of the incentives in climate change policies in the EU are detailed below.

Incentives to reduce GHG emissions include environmental and energy **taxes**, which internalize environmental costs and encourage cleaner alternatives^[10]. Sweden and Germany successfully reduced emissions through **carbon taxes**^[10-12], but their impact was minimal in most EU countries. **Energy taxes** aimed at cutting consumption and boosting efficiency had mixed results: they were effective in Lithuania, the Netherlands, and Spain but failed in the UK and other nations. Their effect on renewable energy adoption also varied, with positive outcomes in France and Lithuania but negative in Hungary^[10]. In general, energy and environmental taxes showed (with some minor exceptions) that the implementation of these measures does not result in a reduction in GHG emissions and did not contribute much to the implementation of climate change policy in EU countries. Taxes could also be used to penalize inefficient behaviours and encourage the adoption of efficient behaviours and technologies^[12].

Investments in **environmental technologies**, such as those improving energy efficiency (EE) and reducing emissions, help lower energy consumption. Regulatory standards that require certain efficiency levels incentivize emission and consumption reductions^[10]. When combined with environmental taxes, these investments can create a multiplier effect on GHG reduction^[11]. Many climate policies focus on setting EE standards in industries, which can cut emissions and energy use^[13]. The emissions trading market further encourages companies to invest in cleaner technologies. Studies show that energy taxes in Cyprus and Italy reduced energy intensity, while in Lithuania, they had a negative effect on EE^[10].

Renewable energy subsidies provide financial support to promote clean technologies ^[10]. Some EU members offer incentives, low-interest loans, for renewable energy projects, which facilitate the adoption of cleaner technologies. Furthermore, these support programs for renewable energy sources help to increase the integration of renewable sources into the energy mix and reduce dependence on fossil fuels, as well as to promote EE improvements ^[14]. The use of EE improvement subsidies allows the industrial and power generation sector to invest in renewable energy and modernize infrastructure, reducing emissions and energy consumption ^[14].

Promoting **sustainable transportation** is another key initiative. Efficient public and private transport systems, along with electric vehicle adoption, help reduce emissions ^[13]. Denmark plans to phase out new diesel and gasoline car sales by 2030, ahead of the EU's 2035 target ^{[15] [16]}. Countries like Estonia and the Netherlands use taxation to encourage public transport use ^[15]. Germany and Sweden have successfully used road and fuel taxes to cut emissions and drive innovation in the automotive sector ^[12].

Another existing example, which is being discussed in the literature, is the **energy savings feed-in tariff (ES FiT)**. This tariff would reward end-users based on the operational return on their investment or behavioural change in terms of energy savings. For example, a US energy company since 2013 that allows its clients to obtain financial credits of \$1.25 for each kWh saved on selected summer days^[12]. A similar approach has been applied in Spain since 2023, where 1CAE (energy savings certificate) is awarded for each kWh saved per year by performing EE improvement actions. In addition, there is a market for CAEs, so additional financial benefits are promoted ^[17].

Awareness-raising programs are essential to educate citizens about climate change and promote sustainable practices. These initiatives have proven effective in changing energy behaviours within communities. Liobikiene's study^[9] on energy taxes found that raising taxes alone is not enough to reduce household energy consumption, particularly if people are not responsive to price changes. Instead, increasing environmental awareness and developing tools for energy efficiency, such as building renovations and electric transportation, are key policy objectives for success.

Information tools, from energy labelling to information campaigns, are a common type of policy adopted by national and local governments to change end-user behaviour^[12]. Information campaigns range from general advertising campaigns on the need to save energy to specific information tailored to specific end-user groups. Specific messages are more effective than generic ones. Bertoldi (2022) notes that energy audits and personal information were shown to be the most effective, followed by information to individuals to compare to other consumers' energy consumption. Information on energy consumption through smart meters, smart billing, and specific devices is another tool recently used to reduce energy consumption, often in conjunction with contest-based or standards-based interventions. Information can contribute to reducing a household's final energy consumption by 5% to 10%^[12].

The role of citizens

All these actions reflect a combined and multidisciplinary effort to achieve reductions in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in line with the European climate objectives. In this context, a literature review^[18] encompassing 2,000 references from 37 articles and books highlights that shifting energy-related behaviours could reduce overall societal energy consumption by approximately 19%.

Although many of the actions ultimately aim to influence behavioural change, it is important to emphasize the need for broad social acceptance of the measures implemented.

Numerous practices have been developed to advance the concept^[19-24]. However, many initiatives framed as efforts to enhance "social acceptance" and promote behavioural change often adopt a paternalistic approach—where the public is expected to comply with what experts have determined to be optimal—or a tokenistic strategy. In the latter, citizens are superficially or symbolically included to project an image of diversity, equality, or participation, while their involvement lacks meaningful influence or decision-making power. These approaches, as stated by Hobman, risk undermining the very goal of fostering genuine engagement and support for renewable energy initiatives^[25].

The trend to orchestrate public engagement actions for social acceptance and/or behavioural changes without a significant empowerment of citizens was confirmed in a study by Chilvers et al.^[20], which analysed 257 public engagement initiatives in low-carbon energy across the UK from 2010 to 2015. The study revealed that most citizen participation efforts remain confined to the lower rungs of Arnstein's Ladder^[26] and are often institutionally driven rather than citizen-led, underscoring a persistent gap in achieving deeper and more transformative engagement.

More recently, in 2018, social innovation in energy transition was defined as an innovation that is social in its means and contributes to a low-carbon energy transition, civic empowerment, and broader social goals related to community well-being^[27]. Since the introduction of the term—and perhaps also motivated by lessons learned from participatory processes implemented up to that point—the literature reveals a growing trend toward mechanisms that enable citizens to co-design their energy transition pathways and develop citizen-driven energy business models^[28-30].

In alignment with this shift towards social innovations in the energy transition, the concept of energy communities^[31, 32] has also emerged as an innovative approach that harnesses citizen involvement in the reconfiguration of energy systems^[33, 34]. These communities, which have gained prominence in recent years, represent a means of organizing collective, citizen-driven energy actions to advance the clean energy transition^[35, 36]. They not only promote decentralized renewable energy production and management but also foster significant public engagement, transforming passive consumers into active co-producers, or even managers of their energy^[37, 38]. According to the European Federation of Citizen Energy Cooperatives, by the end of 2024, there were 2500 European energy cooperatives involving around two million citizens^[35]. Moreover, the European Commission estimated that by 2030 energy communities will hold 17% of wind capacity and 21% of solar capacity^[39].

Although the concept of energy communities is relatively new, the idea of

communities of energy^[40] has existed for decades, empowering citizens as drivers of change and allowing them to take an active role in innovation in various ways. Motivation from citizens to take part in these types of initiatives is explored in the bibliography ^[41, 42]. The novelty of the concept of energy communities may lie in their expanded capacity for diverse activities and their potential to drive genuine social impact, fostering active and meaningful citizen participation.

Undoubtedly, community engagement is a cornerstone for the success of Energy Communities (ECs), as emphasized by various studies. Young et al.^[43] highlight the importance of citizen science principles in rooting these projects while noting that tailored engagement strategies are essential to address challenges like lack of public awareness about energy issues. Similarly, Kallis et al.^[44] identify difficulties in integrating diverse perspectives and local knowledge, urging community-centered approaches to strengthen cohesion and address misconceptions about community needs. Therefore, a critical question arises: to what extent are energy communities being designed as mechanisms for authentic citizen-led initiatives, or are they merely repurposing citizens as passive consumers under a new guise?

Thus, in this context, the AURORA Consortium set out to explore how to create stable citizen hubs that foster more active and inclusive participation in the energy transition, serving as a foundation for driving behavioural change. The project aimed to go beyond traditional outreach or symbolic engagement efforts by designing spaces where citizens are not only informed but also empowered to co-design and co-implement local energy initiatives. The goal was to cultivate long-term civic involvement rooted in trust, knowledge-sharing, and collective ownership of the transition process.

This document reports on the experience gained through the various initiatives developed within the AURORA Project, showcasing strategies aimed at nurturing these citizen hubs. It outlines the methodologies employed, the tools used to encourage collaboration and empowerment, and the lessons learned during implementation. By documenting these practices, the intention is to support their replication in other contexts, contributing to the wider European objective of a just, inclusive, and citizen-driven clean energy transition.

Conceptual Framework: The AURORA rationale

The **AURORA Project** is conceived as a transformative initiative aimed at actively engaging citizens in the development and operation of *citizen science hubs*, with a particular focus on the energy sector. Its core mission is to foster *informed behavioural change* through direct educational actions and participatory practices, empowering individuals and communities to play a leading role in the transition to sustainable energy systems.

At the heart of AURORA lies a four-stage methodology designed to generate meaningful, long-lasting impact:

1. Community Mobilization and Inclusion

The project begins by mobilizing local communities, particularly those aligned with or interested in forming *energy communities*. Recognizing the diversity of social and economic contexts, AURORA is committed to inclusivity by offering flexible participation models. This ensures broad accessibility and encourages the involvement of individuals and groups who might otherwise be excluded from such initiatives.

2. Awareness and Data Democratization

Once communities are engaged, the next step is to raise awareness among participants regarding their energy consumption behaviours. AURORA promotes transparency and shared learning through the open dissemination of data generated by renewable energy installations funded by community members. This data-driven approach empowers citizens with the information they need to make responsible energy decisions.

3. Education and Behaviour Change

A comprehensive suite of educational activities—ranging from hands-on workshops and public lectures to creative competitions and interactive events—is deployed to encourage participants to adopt more sustainable habits. The ultimate objective is to guide individuals toward becoming *Near Zero Emission* citizens, embodying a lifestyle that significantly reduces their environmental footprint.

4. Replication and Scaling through Ambassadors

In the final phase, AURORA seeks to amplify its impact by replicating successful models from its demonstration sites. This is achieved through the creation of a network of **AURORA Ambassadors**—trained individuals who champion the project’s values and methods within their own communities, spreading knowledge and inspiring action across broader geographic and social contexts.

Practical steps

1. Community Mobilization and Inclusion

A key challenge in the creation of citizen hubs is ensuring the active and sustained participation of many people—enough to transform them into ambassadors for behavioural change in the energy transition. The strategy must go beyond simply involving individuals; it must empower them to act collectively as part of a community united by a common purpose.

The proposed approach focuses on the transformation of existing social communities into citizen hubs, acting as decentralized spaces for education, engagement, and experimentation in the context of the energy transition. These hubs provide a platform where citizens can understand not only the environmental impacts of their own energy consumption but also how the production of renewable energy contributes to broader decarbonization goals across Europe.

Through these hubs, citizens are not treated as passive users, but as active participants and co-creators of knowledge and solutions. This model seeks to redefine their relationship with energy—from individual consumers to informed energy citizens capable of shaping local and systemic change.

1.1. Citizen Hub Design Framework

Establishing effective citizen hubs requires a thoughtful design process grounded in two key categories:

- **Operational Principles** – defining how the hub functions and what it stands for
- **Functional Factors** – identifying practical and contextual conditions for success

1.1.1. Operational Principles

These principles guide both the daily operations and long-term vision of citizen hubs. Drawing from Wuebben et al. ^[38], they serve to align citizen participation with scientific inquiry and educational transformation.

Benefits and Values

Citizen hubs generate a range of interconnected benefits, with a particular focus on education and empowerment:

- **Social:** Strengthening community bonds and collective identity
- **Financial:** Encouraging shared investment in community-driven infrastructure
- **Environmental:** Enabling meaningful contributions to climate action through behavioural shifts

Unlike traditional energy communities, citizen hubs are learning spaces built on citizen science principles. Their value proposition includes:

- **Educational:** The primary motivation for participation is knowledge-building. Through citizen science activities—such as data collection, monitoring, and analysis—members gain hands-on understanding of both energy consumption and production across electricity, heating, cooling, and mobility systems.
- **Financial:** While many participants may not directly benefit from reduced energy bills, financial contributions (however modest) increase commitment and help fund visible, shared infrastructure. These investments must be equitable to prevent dominance and maintain trust.
- **Community Building:** Citizen hubs leverage existing social structures to build a sense of purpose and belonging. They act as catalysts for civic empowerment, enabling individuals to drive change within their everyday institutions—be it schools, associations, workplaces, or clubs.

Energy Citizenship and Practices

Citizen hubs are designed to foster energy citizenship, equipping individuals with the knowledge, agency, and opportunities to act on energy issues at both personal and collective levels. Desired practices promoted through the hub include:

- **Energy Conservation:** Reducing consumption by adopting more sustainable habits
- **Renewable Energy Engagement:** Learning about or participating in local energy production
- **Advocacy and Activism:** Influencing public policies or supporting energy transition efforts
- **Awareness and Education:** Sharing insights and resources with peers and networks

- **Community Participation:** Actively shaping hub activities and governance structures

These behaviours are cultivated through engaging, participatory processes grounded in citizen science and inclusive outreach.

Intermediaries

Successful hubs identify intermediaries—key individuals who, although they may not hold formal leadership roles, play a vital part in maintaining trust, cohesion, and participation. These people act as connectors and motivators, facilitating onboarding and sustained involvement.

1.1.2. Functional Factors

These factors define the conditions and environments that make citizen hubs operationally viable and socially impactful.

Location and Community Readiness

Three social foundations must be considered when selecting or forming a citizen hub:

- **Trust:** Confidence in the hub's purpose, leadership, and transparency
- **Community Identity:** A shared sense of belonging and common purpose
- **Social Norms:** Informal but influential expectations that shape behaviors

An effective citizen hub must be embedded in a setting where people feel socially connected and aligned with sustainability goals. It also requires sufficient physical space and a critical mass of engaged participants to support activities and knowledge-sharing.

Universal Participation

Inclusiveness is fundamental. Citizen hubs must extend beyond local neighbourhoods to engage a diverse cross-section of society, aligned with the quadruple helix model— involving citizens, academia, industry, and policymakers.

Design principles to ensure universal participation include:

- **Eliminating participation barriers**, whether social, economic, or informational
- **Actively including vulnerable and marginalized groups**
- **Reframing the hub not only as a tool for cheaper energy, but as a driver of systemic change**

By doing so, citizen hubs become transformative spaces—not only enabling individual behaviour change, but redefining energy culture at the community level.

1.2. Community Feedback and Validation

A crucial phase in the development of citizen hubs is the **collection, analysis, and integration of community feedback**. Engaging citizens in the early stages—through communication campaigns, surveys, interviews, and participatory activities—ensures that the hub is aligned with local motivations, expectations, and capacities. This process also helps identify potential barriers and opportunities for deeper engagement.

1.2.1. Objectives of Community Feedback

The objectives of structured community feedback should include:

- Assessing the **level of perceived responsibility** among citizens regarding energy and climate issues
- Identifying citizens' **motivations** for participating in the hub
- Evaluating **awareness of operational, legal, and technical implications**
- Testing willingness to **contribute financially** or otherwise support the initiative
- Understanding **preferred modes of participation**, such as investment, volunteering, education, or citizen science

Feedback collection must ensure representation across age groups, genders, and professional backgrounds to reflect the diversity of the target community.

1.2.2. Methodological Guidelines

To ensure quality and comparability, the following methodological principles should guide the feedback process:

- **Timing:** Implement feedback in two or more phases (e.g., pre-launch and during pilot operation) to capture evolving perceptions
- **Sample Size:** Aim for statistically significant samples with acceptable confidence levels and margins of error
- **Demographic Balance:** Ensure diversity in terms of age, gender, education, and socioeconomic status
- **Mixed Methods:** Combine quantitative surveys with qualitative discussions or interviews for deeper insight

- **Expression of Interest:** Include mechanisms (e.g., forms or pledges) for respondents to express willingness to contribute time, data, or financial support

1.2.3. Key Indicators to Monitor

Community feedback should be structured around core indicators that reflect the viability and social readiness of the citizen hub:

- **Sense of Co-responsibility:** Proportion of respondents who feel responsible or partially responsible for the energy transition
- **Primary Motivations:** Ranking of motivations such as environmental impact, social benefits, or personal/community involvement
- **Awareness and Expectations:** Level of interest in understanding the legal, financial, and technical aspects of participation
- **Willingness to Invest:** Percentage of respondents open to contributing financially and the range of acceptable investment
- **Support Needs:** Importance placed on having access to technical and legal assistance
- **Participation Preferences:** Distribution of interest across different forms of engagement:
 - Investment
 - Citizen science activities
 - Training and education
 - Volunteering
 - External support or passive interest

1.2.4. Interpretation and Use of Feedback

Feedback must be systematically analysed and integrated into the ongoing design and implementation of the hub. This includes:

- **Adapting engagement strategies** based on preferred participation methods
- **Refining communication** to address areas of low awareness or misunderstanding
- **Adjusting financial models** to match community capacity and willingness
- **Designing inclusive processes** that remove participation barriers for underrepresented or vulnerable groups
- **Identifying potential ambassadors or intermediaries** based on willingness and leadership traits revealed in the responses

1.3. Continuous Engagement and mobilization

The long-term success of citizen hubs depends on their ability to maintain momentum beyond initial phases. Continuous engagement is essential—not only to retain existing

participants, but to grow and evolve the hub into a resilient, adaptive, and socially embedded ecosystem. This requires a strategic approach to mobilization that prioritizes relationship-building, iterative learning, and institutional anchoring.

Dynamic Engagement Strategies

Engagement must be understood as a dynamic process that evolves in response to changing community needs, energy priorities, and contextual challenges. To support this, citizen hubs should implement:

- **Ongoing Communication:** Regular updates, newsletters, and storytelling that keep participants informed and connected to the hub's progress and impact.
- **Iterative Programming:** Rotating themes and activities (e.g., seasonal energy workshops, innovation labs, peer learning events) to maintain relevance and renew interest.
- **Recognition and Incentives:** Acknowledging individual and collective contributions through visible rewards, certifications, or public celebration helps reinforce motivation and pride in participation.

Institutional Integration

To secure durability, hubs must build strong linkages with existing institutions and local governance structures. This includes:

- **Partnerships with Local Authorities:** Formal collaborations that integrate hub initiatives into municipal sustainability plans and policy frameworks.
- **Engagement with Educational Institutions:** Aligning with schools and universities to embed energy literacy and citizen science in curricula and lifelong learning.
- **Industry and SME Collaboration:** Creating shared spaces where businesses can contribute to and benefit from hub activities—whether through technical expertise, sponsorship, or co-creation.

Monitoring and Adaptive Governance

Sustained engagement also depends on a governance model that is transparent, inclusive, and responsive. Key features include:

- **Participatory Governance Structures:** Ensuring that decision-making bodies reflect the diversity of the community and allow for rotating leadership roles.

- **Real-Time Feedback Mechanisms:** Implementing digital platforms or regular forums where members can voice concerns, propose ideas, and co-design solutions.
- **Adaptive Management:** Using monitoring data and feedback to iteratively adjust programming, governance, and outreach strategies.

Scaling and Replication

Finally, successful hubs should serve as prototypes for broader replication. This involves:

- **Documentation of Practices:** Systematic recording of activities, methodologies, and lessons learned to enable knowledge transfer.
- **Mentorship Networks:** Experienced hubs can mentor emerging ones, sharing expertise and resources to accelerate their development.
- **Policy Advocacy:** Leveraging insights and community experiences to inform local and national energy transition policies.

By embedding continuous engagement and mobilization into their core design, citizen hubs can transition from pilot initiatives into enduring pillars of democratic energy governance—empowering citizens as long-term stewards of sustainable change.

1.4. Practical Implementation in AURORA

The following documents illustrate how the AURORA project operationalized concepts related to community modeling, citizen engagement, and systemic transformation. These resources offer practical insights into the implementation of citizen hubs and energy communities across diverse European contexts:

- **Scientific Publication – "Delving into the Modelling and Operation of Energy Communities as Epicenters for Systemic Transformations"**

Authored by A. B. Cristóbal, C. Sanz-Cuadrado, Z. Zhang, and collaborators, this peer-reviewed article (Universal Access in the Information Society, 2023) presents an in-depth exploration of energy communities as strategic instruments for the energy transition. It analyses the socio-technical dynamics underpinning their creation, emphasizing co-governance models, digital infrastructures, and citizen-led experimentation. The study contributes a systems-thinking perspective that supports the design and operation of citizen hubs as decentralized platforms for change.

 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-023-01056-0>

- **Deliverable 2.1 – State of the Art of Energy Mix, Citizens' Behaviours and Environmental Impacts of 5 European Communities**

This internal project deliverable synthesizes baseline data from five AURORA pilot sites, mapping their energy profiles, socio-demographic characteristics, and behavioral trends. It provides a comparative view of the starting conditions that shaped hub implementation and highlights the environmental and cultural diversity within European energy landscapes. These findings were essential for tailoring engagement strategies to local contexts and needs.

- **Deliverable 5.8 – Final Report on Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Activities**

This report outlines the project's approach to stakeholder engagement, knowledge transfer, and long-term impact strategies. It details the communication methodologies used to reach citizens, policymakers, and academic partners, offering lessons learned on how to foster visibility, trust, and participation throughout the project's lifecycle. The deliverable also includes key performance indicators and metrics used to evaluate outreach effectiveness across different media channels.

2. Awareness and Data Democratization

The energy transition is not only a technological and policy challenge—it is fundamentally a social and cultural transformation. For individuals and communities to meaningfully engage with this transition, they must first understand the systems they are a part of. At the core of this understanding lies access to data: information about how energy is produced, consumed, and distributed across their homes, neighbourhoods, and broader networks. Awareness begins when data becomes visible, relatable, and actionable.

Citizen hubs serve as vehicles for this transformation by democratizing access to energy-related data. They enable individuals to visualize their energy consumption, trace their carbon footprints, and connect personal habits to global environmental consequences. But more than that, these hubs create collective experiences around data—spaces where

learning, experimentation, and decision-making are guided by shared information and shared goals.

2.1. The Role of Data in Energy Awareness

Most people do not have a clear sense of how much energy they use, when they use it, or what the environmental implications of that usage are. This disconnect makes it difficult to change habits or adopt more sustainable technologies.

By providing accessible, localized, and real-time data, citizen hubs make energy use visible and meaningful. Whether through smart meters, sensors, or community dashboards, data becomes a mirror reflecting the choices of individuals and groups. It transforms abstract concepts—like kilowatt-hours or emissions per capita—into tangible insights. For example, a household might discover that their peak energy usage coincides with national grid stress, or that installing solar panels could offset the consumption patterns of their street.

In this way, awareness is not just about knowing—it is about noticing. It is the foundation for informed action.

2.2. Principles of Data Democratization

Democratizing data means ensuring that all citizens—not just experts or early adopters—can access, understand, and use energy-related information. For this to happen, citizen hubs must adopt a set of guiding principles:

- **Transparency:** Data should be made publicly available wherever possible, especially when it relates to shared infrastructure or public investments.
- **Accessibility:** Information must be presented in clear, jargon-free formats, using intuitive visualizations and narratives that resonate with diverse audiences.
- **Privacy and Consent:** Personal data must be protected rigorously. Participation in data-sharing must be voluntary and accompanied by informed consent mechanisms.
- **Interoperability:** Data systems should be designed to interact with other platforms, tools, and devices—ensuring scalability and flexibility.
- **Equity of Interpretation:** All participants must have the tools and support needed to interpret data meaningfully, regardless of their technical background.

These principles ensure that data doesn't merely inform—it empowers.

2.3. Data-Driven Tools and Visualizations

To make data meaningful and actionable, citizen energy hubs rely on digital tools that translate raw numbers into lived, local experiences. These tools serve not just to inform,

but to empower communities through engagement and shared insight. Key examples include:

- **Interactive Dashboards:** Community-based platforms where residents can monitor their own energy use, track changes over time, and compare trends across neighbourhoods.
- **Story Maps and Dynamic Visualizations:** Visual tools that bring geographic and temporal data to life—showing energy flows, emissions, and renewable generation in ways that spark local dialogue.
- **Personal Impact Reports:** Tailored summaries that reveal how individual behaviours contribute to collective goals, such as cutting CO₂ emissions or increasing clean energy adoption.

- **Gamified Interfaces:** Engaging systems that use challenges, rewards, and friendly competition to encourage ongoing participation and behavioural change.

These are not passive displays—they are designed for interaction. They invite users to explore scenarios, reflect on their impact, and identify opportunities for meaningful change.

These digital tools do more than presenting data—they actively strengthen the foundation of a citizen energy hub by fostering trust, relevance, and engagement at every level.

By promoting data transparency, interactive dashboards close the information gap between energy operators and local communities. Instead of relying on top-down decisions, citizens gain access to the same insights, enabling shared understanding and collaborative planning.

Through narrative and context, story maps turn complex datasets into accessible visual stories. By connecting data to familiar places and timelines, these tools make the energy transition more tangible, relatable, and open to community dialogue.

Personalization plays a key role as well. Impact reports show individuals how their everyday choices contribute to broader climate targets—such as cutting CO₂ emissions by 55% by 2030. This connection between personal behavior and global goals turns abstract ambitions into concrete, motivating actions.

To keep participation alive over time, gamified elements introduce challenges, rewards, and social recognition. These features not only add a sense of fun, but also foster friendly competition and a shared sense of progress.

When brought together in a single, integrated platform, these tools transform passive data into interactive, community-driven experiences. They empower citizens not just to observe what’s happening—but to take part in shaping their local energy future through informed, collective action.

Category	Example	What it offers	Purpose
Interactive Dashboards	National Grid ESO “Energy Dashboard”	Real-time mix of generation, demand & CO ₂ intensity; open API.	Lets households and communities schedule usage when emissions are lowest.
Interactive Dashboards	CAISO “Today’s Outlook”	Minute-by-minute demand forecast vs. actual and renewable share.	Helps prosumers and aggregators decide when to export or store energy.
Interactive Dashboards	Red Eléctrica “Demanda Peninsular”	Load curve, forecasts and real-time emissions factor for mainland Spain.	Raises citizen awareness of demand peaks and regulated PVPC prices.
Story Maps & Geo-Temporal Visualizations	Mapping Renewable Energy (Esri StoryMap)	Interactive narrative showing where and how renewables are growing.	Great for school workshops or non-technical audiences.
Story Maps & Geo-Temporal Visualizations	An Atlas of Electricity	Timeline + maps illustrating the U.S. grid’s evolution since 1950.	Turns historical data into a story for public debate.
Story Maps & Geo-Temporal Visualizations	IRENA Global Atlas	Solar, wind & bioenergy resource layers with siting filters.	First screening tool for cooperatives seeking community solar/wind sites.
Personal Impact Reports	Opower Home Energy Report	Compares household use to peers and gives tailored tips; 3-5 % savings.	Translates CO ₂ targets into individual action and measures progress.
Personal Impact Reports	Iberdrola “Smart Assistant”	Appliance-level breakdown, alerts & savings projections in app.	Empowers Spanish users without extra hardware—just the app.
Gamified Interfaces	JouleBug	Challenges, points & leaderboards for sustainable actions.	Keeps users engaged in municipal or corporate campaigns.

Gamified Interfaces	Octopus Energy “Saving Sessions”	Flexibility events where customers earn “Octopoints” for lower demand.	Shows gamified demand response can be as effective as backup generation.
Gamified Interfaces	OhmConnect “#OhmHours”	Weekly alerts; less use = points redeemable for cash or devices.	Turns residential demand response into a household “game.”

Table 2. Examples on available data-driven resources

2.4. Learning Through Open Data

Open data becomes a catalyst for collective learning when it is embedded into the culture of the citizen hub. Workshops, participatory research activities, and citizen science projects allow members to engage with data hands-on. For example, a hub might host a monthly “data club” where participants analyse trends in local solar generation or compare energy footprints across public buildings. In doing so, participants are not just recipients of knowledge—they become co-creators of insights.

This process transforms data from a technical asset into a social resource. The act of interpreting and discussing data fosters dialogue, reflection, and a deeper understanding of shared challenges. It also promotes accountability, as community decisions become grounded in evidence and transparent processes.

2.5. Practical Implementation in AURORA: Tools and Outputs

The AURORA project has developed a series of tools and methodologies to support the operationalization of citizen hubs and to empower individuals in actively contributing to the energy transition. The following key outputs illustrate how the project approached the implementation of this phase, focusing on behavioural awareness, citizen engagement, and digital innovation:

- **Deliverable 1.1 - Near-Zero Emissions Citizens Label**

This deliverable presents a structured methodology designed to help citizens assess the impact of their energy-related behaviours in alignment with the objectives of the European Green Deal. The approach enables individuals to evaluate their daily energy choices and identify specific actions that contribute to achieving near-zero emissions, supporting both personal reflection and community-wide benchmarking.

- **Scientific Publication - "A New Approach to Assess Individual Contributions to Energy Transition Goals"**

Authored by C. Sanz-Cuadrado, P. Rahdan, Z. Zhang, M. Victoria, and A. B. Cristóbal (currently under review), this academic paper complements Deliverable 1.1 by proposing a novel framework for quantifying and visualizing individual contributions to both national

and European energy transition targets. The approach integrates behavioural science, energy data modelling, and policy analysis, creating a holistic tool for understanding and motivating citizen involvement in climate goals.

In addition to the core methodology, the paper includes insightful findings on citizens' feedback related to the provision of energy data, revealing both the motivations and reservations individuals have when sharing personal energy usage information. Based on these insights, the paper offers concrete recommendations for policymakers to improve data governance, transparency, and trust in participatory energy systems.

This contribution provides a valuable foundation for scaling citizen science approaches within energy transition frameworks and supports the development of evidence-based policies that are responsive to citizen preferences and concerns.

- **Deliverable 2.2 - AURORA App: A Citizen Science Engagement Tool**

This digital application was developed as a core element of the AURORA citizen hub framework. The app allows users across all 27 EU countries to monitor their energy behaviour patterns and visualize them through an interactive labelling system.

Key features include:

- A personalized dashboard that reflects user-specific energy consumption and behaviour
- A recommendation engine that suggests actionable measures for improvement
- The ability to download anonymized data (in JSON format), supporting transparency and data portability for over 1,600 current users
- The AURORA app not only raises awareness but also enables participatory monitoring and behavioural nudging, turning abstract sustainability goals into tangible, trackable outcomes.

- **Deliverable 2.6 - Final Report on the Use of the AURORA App and Environmental Monitoring**

This final deliverable provides an evaluation of the AURORA app's real-world use and its integration with broader environmental monitoring efforts. It examines how digital tools can complement citizen science hubs by offering real-time feedback, personalized engagement, and community-level data aggregation for informed decision-making.

- **Scientific Publication "The Ethics of Digital Nudging for Sustainable Energy Consumption"**

Authored by Paul Kuyer and published in *Technology in Society* (2025), this peer-reviewed article explores the ethical dimensions of digital nudging as a tool for promoting sustainable energy behaviours. The study examines how digital interfaces—such as apps, platforms, and personalized notifications—can subtly influence user decisions without restricting freedom of choice, a concept that aligns closely with behavioural economics.

The paper raises critical ethical questions related to transparency, autonomy, and power dynamics in digital engagement strategies. Specifically, it challenges designers and policymakers to consider the moral responsibility involved when using data-driven interventions to steer behaviour. These reflections are particularly relevant for the development of citizen hubs, where digital tools and real-time energy feedback are increasingly used to shape individual and collective actions.

Drawing on philosophical analysis and empirical insights, the article provides a set of normative criteria to evaluate when and how digital nudges can be considered ethically justifiable. Its relevance lies in helping citizen-centric initiatives—like those described in this deliverable—ensure that their engagement practices are not only effective but also aligned with democratic values and public trust.

This contribution adds depth to the ongoing conversation about data use, agency, and consent in participatory energy systems, and offers a solid ethical framework for evaluating digital engagement mechanisms within the broader context of the energy transition.

 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2025.102990>

3. Education and Behaviour Change

Citizen hubs are not just platforms for energy data exchange—they are learning environments that seek to reshape the way individuals think, act, and relate to energy. Education, therefore, plays a central role in achieving lasting behavioural change and in cultivating citizens capable of aligning their daily lives with the principles of sustainability.

Rather than focusing solely on the transmission of technical knowledge, the educational strategy within citizen hubs is built around empowerment, experiential learning, and social reinforcement. Through a broad range of activities—ranging from practical workshops to community-driven campaigns—participants are supported in their transition toward becoming Near Zero Emission (NZE) citizens: individuals who adopt low-carbon lifestyles, reduce energy demand, and act as agents of systemic change within their communities.

3.1. Learning Objectives and Behavioural Focus

The educational component of citizen hubs is designed to achieve two interconnected outcomes:

- **Energy literacy:** enabling participants to understand energy systems, technologies, and their environmental implications.
- **Behavioural transition:** supporting the adoption of sustainable habits across energy use, mobility, food consumption, and resource management.

The behavioural focus of these activities is informed by psychological research, behavioural economics, and citizen science practices^[45]. Desired learning outcomes include:

- Awareness of personal and collective energy impact
- Understanding of renewable energy systems and technologies
- Adoption of energy-saving practices at home and in public spaces
- Critical reflection on systemic drivers of climate change
- Willingness to experiment and share knowledge with others

By connecting abstract sustainability targets to daily routines, education becomes a vehicle for internal motivation and collective action.

3.2. Educational Formats and Pedagogical Approaches

Citizen hubs implement a diverse mix of educational formats to respond to the varied learning preferences, skills, and motivations of participants. These include:

- **Hands-on Workshops:** Practical sessions focused on home insulation, smart appliances, solar energy, or sustainable mobility.

Example: The [Energiesprong](#) initiative in the Netherlands offers workshops on net-zero retrofitting techniques, empowering homeowners to understand and implement insulation and renewable upgrades.

Example: The [EcoHome Lab](#) (UK) hosts maker-style sessions on smart home energy monitoring tools and DIY interventions.

- **Public Lectures and Debates:** Expert-led events covering climate policy, ethical consumption, or energy justice, aimed at broadening understanding and stimulating dialogue.

Example: The [Transition Town Totnes](#) group (UK) holds regular public talks on energy justice, local energy systems, and sustainable economics ([Transition Network, 2023](#)).

- **Participatory Science:** Activities that involve citizens in monitoring energy data, co-designing experiments, or validating new low-carbon solutions.

Example: The [Making Sense EU Project](#) involved citizens in Barcelona, Amsterdam, and Pristina to co-design environmental sensors and interpret energy-related data to influence local policy .

Example: The [Citizens4EnergyTransition](#) project in France supported residents to test energy feedback devices and co-develop energy saving experiments.

- **Creative Competitions:** Initiatives such as “energy-saving challenges,” “design your sustainable home,” or “carbon diet contests,” often targeted at youth or families.

Example: The “[Energie-Checker](#)” Challenge in Germany engages school classes in a national competition to reduce school energy consumption, combining STEM learning and behaviour change.

Example: The [Carbon Diet Challenge](#) in Sweden tasks households with reducing their emissions over several weeks, with prizes and feedback sessions.

- **Gamified Learning:** The use of playful, challenge-based, or narrative-driven tools (e.g., mobile apps, simulations, or energy trivia) to enhance engagement and retention.

Example: The [EcoChallenge Platform](#) (US) lets users join themed challenges (climate, mobility, food) and earn points for sustainable actions

Example: The [EnerGAware Project](#) developed a serious game where players manage an energy-efficient virtual home, linked to real energy data in social housing contexts

- **Peer Learning Events:** Story-sharing sessions, roundtables, and community cafés where individuals share experiences and strategies for reducing emissions.

Example: The [Energy Cafés](#) organized by **Tyndall Centre Manchester** and **Carbon Co-op** bring together neighbours to share practical tips and challenges about home retrofits

Example: The “[Climate Conversations](#)” model from Australia uses facilitated dialogues in homes and communities to foster climate literacy and action

- **Energy Communities:** Enabling mechanisms that embed learning within real-life, cooperative initiatives—such as shared solar installations or collective purchasing schemes—where education is tied directly to action and mutual support.

The pedagogical approach is grounded in *learning by doing* and *peer exchange*—ensuring that concepts are contextualized within participants’ lived experiences.

3.3. Behavioural Mechanisms and Change Pathways

To effectively promote sustainable behaviour, educational efforts within citizen hubs are integrated with behavioural design strategies. These include:

- **Personalized Feedback:** Dashboards or apps that provide users with individual energy profiles, consumption trends, and low-carbon recommendations.
- **Social Comparison:** Visualizations that allow participants to compare their performance with community averages or top-performing peers.
- **Goal Setting:** Encouraging the formulation of personal or group energy-saving targets, often supported by pledges or action plans.
- **Positive Reinforcement:** Public recognition, digital badges, or symbolic rewards for consistent participation or achievements.
- **Default Options:** Nudges embedded in apps or services that promote more sustainable choices as the default (e.g., auto-suggesting greener mobility modes).
- **Narrative Engagement:** Framing behaviour change as part of a shared journey toward resilience, justice, and collective wellbeing.

These mechanisms help translate awareness into action by reducing friction, increasing motivation, and making change socially visible.

3.4. Practical Implementation in AURORA: Tools and Outputs

As part of its commitment to ensuring the long-term sustainability of citizen-led energy initiatives, the AURORA project also developed and assessed a series of business models and engagement strategies tailored to the unique characteristics of each participating energy community. These efforts were documented through targeted deliverables and scientific outputs, which provide both theoretical frameworks and practical insights into how citizen science can be translated into sustainable, scalable practices.

- **Deliverable D3.1 – Report on the Business Models to Follow-Up by the Different Local Energy Communities**

This deliverable presents a comprehensive analysis of viable business models that can support the continuity and expansion of local energy communities (LECs) beyond the AURORA project timeline. Drawing on a thorough bibliographic review and contextual analysis, the report proposes tailored business models aligned with the specific regulatory, economic, and social conditions of each AURORA pilot site.

The document explores a variety of models—such as cooperative ownership structures, energy-as-a-service approaches, and community benefit schemes—evaluating their feasibility in different local contexts. It emphasizes participatory governance, financial viability, and long-term impact, offering each community a concrete roadmap for future operations.

- **Scientific Publication – “Business Models for Citizen-Led Renewable Energy Initiatives”**

Published in *Solar RRL*, this peer-reviewed article extends the findings of Deliverable D3.1 by formalizing a typology of business models specifically adapted to citizen-led renewable energy projects. The paper systematically assesses the opportunities and barriers associated with each model, and proposes policy mechanisms to enhance citizen participation and reduce investment risk. It offers a significant contribution to the literature on energy democratization and local empowerment in the context of the EU Green Deal.

 <https://doi.org/10.1002/solr.202300498>

- **Book Chapter – “Aprendizaje activo y basado en retos: el caso del proyecto AURORA de ciencia ciudadana”**

Included in the volume *Innovación docente universitaria para un aprendizaje efectivo: experiencias que transforman* (ISBN: 979-13-7011-152-6), this chapter documents the pedagogical innovations implemented within AURORA. It focuses on challenge-based and active learning methodologies used to engage students in real-world problem-solving related to the energy transition. The chapter illustrates how the project’s educational framework reinforced both scientific literacy and civic engagement, contributing to the formation of a new generation of energy-conscious citizens.

- **Deliverable D4.3 – Creating AURORA Ambassadors for Sustainable Energy Behaviours: Interventions Developed and Linked Impact**

This final deliverable offers a detailed account of the behavioural interventions deployed across the AURORA pilot sites. The report outlines strategies aimed at motivating individuals to adopt more sustainable energy practices, including gamified challenges, community events, and targeted communication campaigns.

Crucially, the document synthesizes feedback collected from citizens, providing an evidence-based assessment of which interventions had the strongest impact on behaviour change. It also captures insights from community discussions about future engagement strategies, highlighting a collective preference for interventions that are localized, inclusive, and action oriented.

- **Scientific Publication – “Lessons Learned From Establishing a Rooftop Photovoltaic System Crowdsourced by Students and Employees at Aarhus University”**

Published in *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, this scientific article identifies and analyzes the ten most significant challenges encountered when establishing a university-based energy community. Drawing on practical experience from the AURORA project, the authors describe the specific strategies adopted to overcome these obstacles, offering a valuable roadmap for other institutions aiming to create their own citizen-led energy initiatives.

Beyond operational insights, the paper provides concrete policy recommendations targeted at the European, national, and municipal levels, aimed at facilitating the legal, financial, and social conditions necessary for the widespread deployment of energy communities. The publication serves as both a reflective case study and a policy-oriented guide, contributing to the broader adoption of community-driven renewable energy systems across academic and civic contexts.

 <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/pip.70009>

- **AURORA Guide for Citizen Workshops on Energy Matter.**

4. Replication and Scaling through Ambassadors

In the final phase of implementation, the hub aims to extend its impact beyond initial pilot sites by enabling the replication of successful citizen hub models. This is not done through top-down mandates or rigid blueprints, but rather through a flexible, human-centered approach centered on the creation of a distributed network of Ambassadors. These individuals serve as local multipliers, equipped with the knowledge, tools, and values

needed to inspire others and adapt the hub model to new geographical and social contexts.

Ambassadors are more than facilitators—they are catalysts of cultural and behavioural transformation, anchoring the energy transition in the communities they serve.

4.1. Strategic Role of Ambassadors in the Energy Transition

Ambassadors play a key role in diffusing the practices and ethos of AURORA across regions. Positioned within their own social and professional ecosystems, they act as trusted messengers and initiators of change.

Their primary functions include:

- Promoting awareness of the energy transition
- Sharing knowledge and tools developed;
- Facilitating the creation of new citizen hubs or energy-focused initiatives;
- Acting as connectors between citizens, institutions, and technical actors.

By embodying the behaviours and principles they advocate for, ambassadors help normalize low-carbon lifestyles and expand the reach of participatory approaches.

4.2. Selection and Training Framework

Ambassadors should be carefully selected and supported through a structured training process that equips them to lead with credibility, inclusion, and effectiveness.

Selection Criteria:

- Demonstrated motivation and community involvement;
- Ability to engage diverse audiences;

- Representation across age groups, genders, and socio-economic backgrounds.

Training Components:

- Core concepts of climate change, energy systems, and sustainability;
- Facilitation and communication skills;
- Use of the hub tools;
- Ethics of engagement and inclusive practices;
- Leadership, storytelling, and community organizing.

Upon completion, ambassadors receive formal recognition—such as a certificate or digital badge—and ongoing access to support networks and learning resources.

4.3. Mechanisms for Local Replication

Ambassadors are empowered to initiate and lead locally tailored activities based on the hub model. Rather than replicating infrastructure, they replicate values, processes, and community engagement strategies.

Mechanisms include:

- Use of open-source toolkits and replication guides developed by the project.
- Adaptation of hub activities to reflect local culture, needs, and capacities.
- Launch of micro-hubs or pilot initiatives in schools, workplaces, or neighbourhoods.
- Collaboration with local authorities and civil society groups to gain legitimacy and support.

This flexible, decentralized model ensures that the replication process remains community-driven while aligned with the core principles of the AURORA approach.

4.4. Network Building and Peer Support

Ambassadors do not operate in isolation—they are part of a dynamic community of practice. The hub fosters this collective dimension through:

- Regular ambassadors meet-ups (online and in-person) to exchange insights and challenges;
- Collaborative campaigns and shared thematic missions.
- Peer mentorship between experienced and newly trained ambassadors.
- A digital platform for sharing resources, updates, and impact stories.

These peer structures not only prevent burnout but also promote learning, innovation, and a shared sense of purpose.

4.5. Practical Implementation: Tools and Outputs from AURORA

The AURORA project has developed several resources to support ambassador engagement and scaling efforts. These include:

As part of its strategy to scale the impact of citizen-led initiatives and promote long-term civic engagement, the AURORA project launched a dedicated programme to train and support local Ambassadors—individuals empowered to promote sustainable energy behaviours within their communities. To guide this process, a set of tools and resources were developed to ensure transparency, replicability, and effective outreach.

- **Guide for Applicants – AURORA Ambassadors**

This guide outlines the benefits, responsibilities, and opportunities available to those interested in becoming AURORA Ambassadors. It provides detailed information on the programme’s objectives, the training and capacity-building sessions offered, and the expected level of commitment. The document serves as a comprehensive introduction to the ambassador initiative, facilitating informed decision-making for prospective participants.

 [Guide for Applicants](#)

- **Public Recognition Platform for Ambassadors**

In recognition of the individuals who commit to becoming active facilitators of the energy transition, AURORA established a dedicated webpage to showcase their involvement. This platform not only acknowledges their contribution publicly, but also helps build a sense of community, visibility, and accountability among the network of ambassadors.

 [AURORA Ambassadors Public Recognition](#)

- **Welcome Webinar – Introduction to the Ambassador Programme**

To ensure alignment and motivation from the outset, a welcome webinar was recorded and made publicly available. This session provides an overview of the AURORA project, the strategic role of ambassadors, and the tools they will have at their disposal. It also includes testimonials and practical insights from early participants, serving as a valuable onboarding tool.

 [Watch the Webinar](#)

- **Deliverable 4.3 – Creating AURORA Ambassadors for Sustainable Energy Behaviours: Interventions Developed and Linked Impact**

This deliverable presents a detailed account of the interventions designed to train and activate the ambassador network. It documents the methodologies used, the behaviour changes strategies implemented across pilot sites, and the measurable impacts observed. The report highlights how localized engagement, supported by structured facilitation, can lead to sustained behavioural transformation and community empowerment.

10 final key recommendations for creating citizen energy hubs

- 1 Build on existing communities:** Start with groups that already share an identity (universities, neighbourhoods, associations) and co-design the hub from day one. Identify and empower the informal “connectors” who foster trust and sustained engagement.
- 2 Practise radical inclusivity:** Set explicit diversity goals (age, gender, income, background) and remove economic, digital, or time barriers. Offer multiple levels of involvement—volunteering, investment, citizen science, leisure—so everyone finds a doorway in.
- 3 Democratise energy data:** Give every participant simple, real-time, visual access to their consumption and the community’s renewable generation. Prioritise transparency, interoperability, and data-privacy safeguards to build long-term trust.
- 4 Deliver personalised, actionable advice:** Pair the raw data with a recommendation engine that turns numbers into concrete steps.
- 5 Learn by doing: blend citizen science, challenges, and play:** Combine hands-on workshops (insulation, self-consumption, e-mobility) with gamified challenges and collective data-analysis sessions. Experiential learning and social comparison accelerate habit change.
- 6 Embed the energy-community concept from the start:** Explain the legal, financial, and technical routes for sharing renewable generation. Showing people, they can be co-owners—not just consumers—boosts both belonging and climate ambition.
- 7 Adopt participatory, adaptive governance:** Create open decision spaces, rotate leadership roles, and track clear indicators (motivations, willingness to invest, savings achieved) to adjust activities continuously.
- 8 Create and nurture an ambassador network:** Select motivated individuals, train them in communication, data, and facilitation, and give them public visibility. Their mission is to spark micro-hubs, support new groups, and keep the learning culture alive.
- 9 Communicate with local stories and multi-channel outreach:** Mix relatable narratives (testimonials, neighbourhood wins) with impactful data and use the channels your community already follows (WhatsApp, school radio, physical noticeboards). Steady storytelling feeds commitment.
- 10 Document, share, and standardise resources:** Publish open guides, business-model templates, survey forms, and impact results. Making replication easy saves effort for future hubs and turns a single project into a growing movement.

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